

Terpenoids. Part LXVIII. Synthesis of dl-Hotrienol

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Synthesis of dl-hotrienol has been accomplished through the application of Wittig reaction with β -methallylidetriphenyl-phosphorane on the suitably substituted aldehyde for the creation of the conjugated diene system present in the compound.

Hotrienol, an acyclic monoterpene *tert.*-alcohol, has been isolated from Japanese Ho-Leaf oil¹ obtained from the young plants of Ho-Sho tree also known as "East Linalool tree" (*Cinnamomum camphora* Sieb. subsp. *formosana* var. *orientalis* subvar. *linaloola* Hirota) according to Hirota² were brought from Formosa.

On the basis of chemical and spectroscopic data¹ constitution (I) has been proposed for hotrienol. The salient features of the structure are the presence of 2 : 4-disubstituted diene system at one end and the vinyl group at the other end of the acyclic molecule, the double bond at 5 : 6-position being *trans* as shown by the IR absorption peak at 965 cm^{-1} .

In the present communication, we report a synthesis of dl-hotrienol which involves the use of Wittig reaction for the generation of the 2 : 4-disubstituted diene system as a cardinal step. The sequence of reactions employed for the synthesis are shown in the chart given below :

CHART I:- SEQUENCE OF REACTIONS LEADING TO THE FORMATION OF dl-HOTRIENOL

2-Methyl-5 : 5-ethylenedioxy hexane-2 : 3-diol (III), the starting material, was secured by the neutral potassium permanganate oxidation³ of 2-methyl-5 : 5-ethylenedioxy-2-hexane⁴ in 29 per cent yield. The diol (III) upon oxidation with lead tetraacetate in dry benzene according to the conditions of Yonovskayo *et al.*⁵ provided 3 : 3-ethylenedioxy butyraldehyde (IV) in 58% yield. The aldehyde (IV) was characterised through its semicarbazone derivative which melted at 205°. The sharp smelling aldehyde (IV) was subjected to Wittig reaction⁶ with β -methallylidetriphenylphosphorane when 2-methyl-6 : 6-ethylenedioxy-1 : 3-heptadiene (V) was obtained in 55% yield. The product was chromatographed over neutral alumina when elution with pet. ether (40°-60°) provided the pure diene. IR spectrum showed absorption at 965 cm^{-1} implying the presence of the *trans* disubstituted double bond. The ketal-diene, thus obtained, on deketalisation with aqueous hydrochloric acid in acetone gave the keto-diene (VI) which when subjected to Grignard reaction⁷ with vinyl magnesium bromide in THF afforded 3 : 7-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1 : 5 : 7-octatriene (I) in 55% yield.

The identity of the synthesised alcohol was established through the comparison of its IR and UV spectrum with those reported in literature¹.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Methyl-5 : 5-ethylenedioxy hexane-2 : 3-diol (III) : 2-Methyl-5 : 5-ethylenedioxy-2-hexene⁴ (II, 30.0 g.) in water (1400 ml.) was cooled in an ice bath (0°). To this mixture, vigorously stirred, was slowly added (2 hr.) potassium permanganate solution (320 ml., 8%) and stirred for further one hr. The reaction mixture was heated on a water bath (100°), where it set to a gel prior to the precipitation of manganese dioxide. The mixture was filtered, filtrate concentrated under rotary evaporator and the concentrate after treatment with anhydrous potassium carbonate (65 g.) was extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried (anhyd. Na_2SO_4) and solvent evaporated. The residue on careful fractionation under reduced pressure furnished the diol (III, 10.6 g.) in 29% yield, b.p. 140°-50°/10-15 mm, η_D^{25} 1.4520. (Found : C, 56.70; H, 9.35. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 56.84; H, 9.47%). IR spectrum showed characteristic bands at 3450, 1130, 1100 cm^{-1} (hydroxy) and 1045 cm^{-1} (ketal).

3 : 3-Ethylenedioxy butyraldehyde (IV) : Lead tetraacetate (20.0 g.) was added in small lots at 16°-27° to a stirred solution of the diol (III, 10.0 g.) in dry benzene (250 ml.). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 hr. and filtered. Finally powdered potassium carbonate was added to the filtrate which was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue distilled under vacuum to afford the sharp smelling aldehyde (IV, 3.95 g.) in 58% yield, b.p. 60°-70°/5-6 mm., η_D^{25} 1.4290. The aldehyde was characterised through its semicarbazone derivative which melted at 205°. (Found : C, 55.52; H, 7.71. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 55.38; H, 7.69%). The aldehyde (IV) showed characteristic IR absorption peaks at 2730, 1720 cm^{-1} (aldehyde) and 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal).

2-Methyl-6 : 6-ethylenedioxy-1 : 3-heptadiene (V) : The methallylidetriphenylphosphorane was prepared from methallyltriphenylphosphonium chloride (14.35 g.) in DMSO

* Melting point and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer with sodium chloride optics using a thin liquid film. Microanalysis by Mr. L. K. Khullar, Microanalyst of our department.

(40 ml.) and NaH (1.96 g., 50%) in DMSO (20 ml.) under nitrogen atmosphere. To this was then added the aldehyde (IV, 3.5 g.) in THF (5 ml.). The contents were stirred for 30 min. at room temperature and then warmed on a water bath at 40° for another 30 min. and left overnight at room temperature. The contents were poured on crushed ice and extracted with pet. ether (40°–60°). The ether extract was dried, solvent removed and the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina when elution with pet. ether (40°–60°) gave the diene (V) which was further purified by distillation under reduced pressure, b.p. 110°/5–6 mm., yield 2.5 g. (55%). (Found : C, 71.13; H, 9.45. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.43; H, 9.52%). IR spectrum showed IR bands at 1640, 1600 cm^{-1} (conjugated diene), 3070, 880 cm^{-1} (gem-disubstituted methylene), 1060 cm^{-1} (ketal) and 965 cm^{-1} (*trans*-disubstituted double bond).

2-Methyl-1 : 3-heptadiene-6-one (VI) : 2-Methyl-6 : 6-ethylenedioxy-1 : 3-heptadiene (V, 1.0 g.) was dissolved in acetone (20 ml.) and mixed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (5 ml., 10%) and the reaction mixture allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hr. The solution was diluted with saturated brine solution (10 ml.) and the product taken up in ether, dried and distilled under vacuum to obtain 2-methyl-1 : 3-heptadiene-6-one (VI, 9.6 g.) in 81% yield, b.p. 95°–100°/5–6 mm. (Found : C, 77.10; H, 9.32. $C_8H_{12}O$ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.68%). IR spectrum showed prominent peaks at 1640, 1600 cm^{-1} (conjugated diene), 1720 cm^{-1} (carbonyl), 3070, 890 cm^{-1} (gem disubstituted methylene) and 965 cm^{-1} (*trans* disubstituted double bond).

3 : 7-Dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1 : 5 : 7-octatriene (I) : To the Grignard reagent prepared from vinyl bromide (1.1 g.), magnesium (0.24 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (70 ml.) was added dropwise the ketone (VI, 0.6 g.) in cold. After standing overnight the reaction mixture was decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution, water and dried (anhyd. Na_2SO_4). The solvent was evaporated and the residue distilled under vacuum to furnish 3 : 7-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1 : 5 : 7-octatriene (I, 0.34 g.) in 55% yield, b.p. 90°–95°/5–6 mm. η_D^{30} 1.4870. (Lit.³ η_D^{20} 1.4913) λ_{max}^{EtOH} 230 $m\mu$ (Lit.³ λ_{max}^{EtOH} 230 $m\mu$). (Found : C, 78.80; H, 10.42. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.95; H, 10.53%). IR spectrum showed peaks at 3550, 3070, 2950, 1645, 1605, 1450, 1370, 1160, 1115, 985, 960, 915, 730 and 690 cm^{-1} comparable to those reported in literature¹.

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